

One 4Health SURVEILLANCE

Deliverable 4.1 Interim Sustainability Report

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Executive Summary

This interim report presents an overview of the preliminary observations related to sustainability within the OH4Surveillance project during its first 18 months. Sustainability has been a central consideration from the project's inception, and this report outlines how that focus has translated into actions, reflections, and emerging lessons.

A combination of strong national engagement and commitment from institutions, has facilitated early sustainability observations. Furthermore, the observations made thus far have also revealed several challenges—most notably in securing sustainable funding, addressing infrastructure deficiencies, and harmonising collaborative mechanisms across countries. The insights reported here are drawn from working group activities, project meetings, and a questionnaire survey conducted among consortium partners. This report lays the groundwork for the Final Sustainability Report (D4.2), due at project end, which will provide more comprehensive and consolidated recommendations.

1. Introduction

The majority of new emerging infectious diseases that affect humans are zoonoses, infections that can be transmitted between animals and humans. There are many factors that drive the emergence and spread of zoonotic diseases, and it has become evident that animal health, human health and the environment are interconnected. Therefore, there is a pressing need for more rapid and effective responses to zoonotic diseases, which can be achieved with a conceptual shift from siloed approaches towards a One Health approach. The surveillance on the animal health side and in the environment need to be scaled up to set up a One Health surveillance for emerging and re-emerging pathogens. Ideally, this is done in collaboration across countries.

The general objective of OH4Surveillance ('Setting up a coordinated surveillance under the One Health approach') is to support the participating countries to set up and scale up One Health surveillance to priority pathogens in an efficient, coordinated and collaborative manner. The project includes capacity building and surveillance activities. OH4Surveillance comprises of 11 beneficiaries and 11 affiliated entities and is coordinated by Statens Serum Institut (SSI).

Work package 4 of OH4Surveillance is responsible for sustainability and aims to keep sustainability of the project activities in focus by regularly discussing it with project participants and stakeholders. It also works to identify both key enablers and challenges for the sustainability of activities, structures, and infrastructures. Overall, WP4 ensures that sustainability considerations are part of the project from the beginning to the end, contributing to long-lasting results and impact.

This Interim Sustainability Report (Deliverable D4.1) covers the first 18 months of project implementation. It provides an initial assessment of the activities and strategies undertaken to ensure that the surveillance capacities, structures, and collaborations built during the project are maintained beyond its duration. The report identifies facilitators and challenges encountered so far, outlines measures already taken or planned to overcome barriers, and offers early recommendations to enhance sustainability.

The findings are based on extensive interactions across consortium meetings, work package collaborations, and discussions. In connection to the Project Meeting in February 2025, a short questionnaire was disseminated to all project partners. The survey gathered responses from 35 participants representing all partner countries and a diversity of institutional perspectives. The survey explored perceptions around surveillance improvements, collaboration mechanisms, sustainability barriers, and future needs. Many respondents provided thoughtful qualitative feedback, including reflections on existing or newly formed national coordination structures, suggestions for strengthening cross-border collaboration, and concerns about sustained funding.

This report sets the foundation for the Final Sustainability Report (D4.2), due at the project's conclusion, which will focus on lessons learned and propose consolidated sustainability strategies for the future.

2. Sustainability Strategy Overview

The project's sustainability strategy is deeply rooted in the EU4Health ambitions and aims to embed the One Health approach in national and regional surveillance systems. It emphasises capacity building, collaborative structures, and integration with policy priorities. OH4Surveillance contributes directly to better preparedness for cross-border health threats by supporting countries establish scalable and coordinated surveillance systems.

In OH4Surveillance, sustainability is not treated as a final consideration but rather as a continuous focus. The project draws strength from collaborations with national and European stakeholders and seeks complementarity with other initiatives and projects. By aligning efforts and finding synergies, OH4Surveillance enhances the chances of institutional uptake and enduring impact.

3. Sustainability in Focus in Activities and Meetings

Throughout the first 18 months, significant steps have been taken to reinforce sustainable practices. These include targeted capacity building initiatives, such as technical workshops, national trainings, and cross-partner exchanges, which have enhanced skills and created a shared understanding of surveillance priorities. Improvements to surveillance infrastructure have also been observed, often leveraging existing national systems while building in OH4Surveillance-specific enhancements.

Working groups around the prioritised pathogens have been established, successfully fostering a strong network of experts across countries and disciplines. These networks that share knowledge and experience directly facilitating the setting up of surveillance protocols in other countries and are foreseen to continue beyond the lifetime of this project.

The Sustainability Working Group is used for integrating long-term thinking and international aspects into the project's sustainability activities.

Furthermore, a questionnaire together with WP3 was circulated to consortium participants giving them an opportunity to provide their thoughts on sustainability, among other things.

Table 1. Sustainability has been discussed in several meetings

Meeting Name	Date(s)	Location	Notes/Relation to Sustainability
OH4Surveillance Kick-Off Meeting	27–28 February 2024	Copenhagen, Denmark	Initial project set-up; sustainability embedded into WP4, early identification of needs for lasting structures.
4th EFSA BIOHAW One Health Surveillance Subgroup Meeting	4–5 November 2024	Online	One Health subgroup; discussion on sustainable surveillance systems and data sharing frameworks. Invitation to join OH4Surveillance Sustainability Working Group.
OH4Surveillance Project Meeting	25–26 February 2025	Uppsala, Sweden	Review of progress including sustainability activities; preliminary findings for interim sustainability report discussed.
OH4Surveillance Steering Board and General Assembly Meetings	26 February 2025	Uppsala, Sweden	Strategic discussions on ensuring project outcomes, including sustainability strategies beyond project funding.
Meeting of the project OH-Allies	19–24 March 2025	Dublin, Ireland	Networking with wider One Health community; sustainability approaches for integrated surveillance discussed.

4. Sustainability: Facilitators and Challenges

4.1 Facilitators Identified

Several factors have positively influenced the sustainability of the OH4Surveillance project work in its first 18 months. An important factor for long-term sustainability is the project's alignment with broader EU-level strategies and One Health objectives. A good example of this is the coordinated data reporting to European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).

Questionnaire survey respondents provided feedback on which factors are likely to support the continuation and long-term impact of OH4Surveillance activities at national and cross-border levels after the project ends. Their responses have shed light on the institutional, technical, and policy-level conditions that help embed surveillance efforts into long-term frameworks.

Many reported that there has been strong national institutional support where existing collaboration mechanisms between stakeholders have either been strengthened or newly established through OH4Surveillance activities, and the hope is that collaboration will continue to be strengthened.

Several external enablers were identified that may support the continuation and integration of OH4Surveillance efforts after the project ends. A recurring theme in the survey responses was the importance of international networking and structured cross-border coordination. Respondents highlighted that opportunities to engage with peers from other national institutions have helped establish professional relationships and fostered a shared vision for future collaboration. These emerging networks are viewed as a key asset for maintaining momentum and collaboration beyond the project's lifecycle.

4.2 Barriers and Challenges Identified

While many of the project's activities are considered valuable to ensure sustainability, several barriers were identified that could hinder the long-term continuation of OH4Surveillance efforts once the project concludes.

A recurrent challenge reported in the survey was the absence of dedicated national funding mechanisms to maintain or scale up surveillance activities developed through the project. Some respondents explicitly noted that no clear financial pathways exist to support the continuation of improved One Health collaboration or surveillance infrastructure beyond the project period. This reflects a broader concern that without targeted follow-up investment, there is a risk of losing the momentum created during the initial implementation phase.

In addition to financial issues, institutional and operational barriers were also raised. Several respondents indicated that while initial coordination structures have been strengthened, formal mechanisms for long-term cross-sector collaboration—especially involving public health and veterinary authorities—remain either underdeveloped or informal. Some

mentioned that collaboration depends heavily on personal networks and might not be sustained without more formalised governance frameworks.

Finally, a number of respondents indicated that there is still a need for more regular exchanges of knowledge, experiences, and practices and stronger cross-border alignment. In particular, national-level preparedness strategies are often developed in isolation, and one respondent recommended “*joint policy strategies*” as a way to support more integrated regional approaches.

In summary, the barriers to sustainability identified so far are multifaceted—spanning financial, institutional, and strategic levels—and addressing them will be crucial for ensuring that the project’s achievements are not only maintained but built upon in the future.

The sustainability of OH4Surveillance outcomes beyond the project period may be affected by a number of risks. A primary concern raised by several partners is the risk of losing momentum once project funding comes to an end. Without follow-up investment or integration into national budgets, there is a real possibility that newly established collaborations and capacities may not be maintained.

This risk is compounded by challenges such as staff turnover and limited institutional memory. In some cases, continuity may depend heavily on individual actors rather than established systems, making long-term impact vulnerable to organizational change. A further risk relates to the limited alignment between project outputs and national strategies, which could hinder the broader adoption of tools, processes, or recommendations developed through the project.

In response, the project has taken steps to encourage more structured engagement with national stakeholders, including the recommendation that partners begin internal planning for sustaining key elements beyond the project’s duration. These efforts are consistent with the overall risk management approach outlined in the Grant Agreement and reflect a proactive strategy to safeguard the value and relevance of OH4Surveillance’s contributions over time.

5. Recommendations

Building on the insights gathered from project meetings, working group discussions, and the mid-term questionnaire, several targeted recommendations can be made to support the sustainability of OH4Surveillance activities beyond the project period.

At the national level, a key recommendation is to formalise cross-sector collaboration through institutional mandates or agreements that extend beyond the project’s lifetime. While some countries already have frameworks in place, others noted in the questionnaire that no formal structure has been established and that coordination remains ad hoc or depend on personal networks.

Several respondents highlighted the importance of building on existing collaboration structures rather than creating new, parallel systems. Respondents also stressed the need

for early and continuous engagement with policy makers, stakeholders and the public, to raise awareness about project outcomes and secure buy-in for their long-term relevance.

In terms of technical sustainability, partners underscored the importance of investing in infrastructure that enables effective data sharing and interoperability. Several respondents identified barriers related to data compatibility and the limitations of existing digital infrastructure. Challenges in sharing surveillance data across the animal, environmental, and human health sectors were mentioned, with particular reference to incompatible platforms and unclear data governance arrangements. To support sustainable collaboration, it will be important to improve cross-sector data flows and develop solutions tailored to national contexts.

Furthermore, peer learning and cross-country collaboration were highlighted by respondents as important contributors to long-term sustainability. Many noted that observing how other countries organise their One Health surveillance systems, especially through project meetings and informal exchanges, provided useful insights and inspiration for shaping their own national approaches. Several responses expressed a clear desire for continued opportunities to engage with counterparts in other countries, particularly within the public health sector. This type of interaction was seen as not only beneficial for knowledge sharing but also for strengthening professional networks that could endure beyond the project period. While some partners suggested that greater policy alignment across countries might support future collaboration, others emphasised the value of flexible collaboration formats adapted to national priorities. Building on this feedback, initiatives such as cross-country exchanges, joint workshops, and thematic forums could play a key role in maintaining dialogue and supporting sustainability after project funding has ended.

In summary, strengthening sustainability requires a combination of institutional commitment, technical interoperability, and structured international engagement. These actions—grounded in partner experiences and insights—can help secure the continuity and long-term impact of OH4Surveillance work.

6. Conclusions

At the halfway point of OH4Surveillance, sustainability considerations have been well integrated into project activities, both at the strategic and operational levels.

There is clear evidence of positive developments towards sustainability: national-level structures for collaboration are being strengthened, and many partners have gained a broader understanding of the requirements for long-term One Health surveillance. External alignment with European priorities and agencies adds further support for the uptake and relevance of project outputs and achievements.

Nevertheless, sustainability remains vulnerable to a range of structural and institutional challenges. In particular, the absence of dedicated funding mechanisms, varying levels of technical capacity, and the informal nature of some collaborative arrangements may pose risks to continuity. These concerns have been acknowledged by partners, who also

suggested practical ways forward, including stronger engagement with policy makers, improvements in data sharing, and continued peer learning across borders.

Looking ahead, the next phase of the project will be critical for translating these early insights into actionable strategies. As the funding aspects rises concern for the long term implementation of technical outputs, partners still have an important role in articulating needs and priorities, contribute to advancing elements that are less dependent on funding—such as maintaining networks, and fostering cross-border collaboration—which are critical for ensuring continued impact , and maintaining open dialogue on long-term priorities. These efforts will culminate in the Final Sustainability Report (D4.2), which will consolidate lessons learned and outline a roadmap for preserving and building on OH4Surveillance achievements beyond the project's conclusion.